

LIPID-LOWERING EFFECT OF CASSIA FISTULA EXTRACT IN HIGH FAT DIET INDUCED HYPERLIPIDEMIA

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Abstract

Dyslipidemia, also known as hypercholesterolemia, is a chronic metabolic illness marked by an excess of fats or lipids in the blood, which can cause atherosclerosis and eventually chronic heart disease (CHD). The goal of the current investigation was to ascertain the therapeutic potential of Cassia fistula leaf extract against fat accumulation and dyslipidemia in obese rats caused by a high-fat diet. There were thirty rats and were split into five groups of six rats at random. Accordingly, a number of biochemical parameters were assessed, including lipid profiles, health indicators, and antioxidants. Additionally, a liver histopathology study was performed. Leaf aqueous extract dramatically improves health indicators and lipid profiles. Hepatocyte steatosis, fat accumulation, and RBC infiltration are all caused by a high-fat diet, according to histopathological study of the liver. In addition to improving lipid metabolism, boosting antioxidant defense and restoring histopathological alteration, the results of the current study showed that Cassia fistula leaf extract prevent fat accumulation and dyslipidemia by inhibiting impaired lipid digestion and absorption.

INTRODUCTION

Due to their greater compatibility, lower side effects, and cost-effectiveness, the use of herbal medicinal plants is becoming more popular than conventional therapy. Alkaloids, flavonoids, and terpenoids are among the many bioactive substances found in plants that have analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties (Singh and Gohil, 2024).

One of the most prevalent metabolic diseases, hyperlipidemia is defined by abnormal blood lipid levels, such as total cholesterol (TC) and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), triglycerides (TG), and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C). One of the main biological predictors of atherosclerotic cardiovascular diseases (ASCVD), including myocardial infarction and ischemic stroke,

is hyperlipidemia with high LDL and TG values (Sajid et al., 2025a). A high-fat diet is thought to be the cause of the increase in cholesterol and fat in the body, which leads to dyslipidemia and related cardiovascular diseases. Dyslipidemia, which is defined as an elevated level of serum total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), low density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), and decreased level of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), leads to the majority of cardiovascular diseases and varies in prevalence around the world, with an estimated 50% of adults suffering from it.

HDL-C levels and slightly elevated LDL-C are characterized by abnormal blood concentrations of TC, TG, HDL-C, and LDL-C (Bello-Ovosi et al., 2019). The burden of cardiovascular disease dyslipidemia has significantly lowered due to lipid-lowering drugs, especially statins used in conjunction with other treatments such bile acid sequestrants like ezetimibe. Common characteristics of diabetes linked to dyslipidemia include elevated TG, LDL-C, and decreased HDL-C values. Increases of 25–35% in TG, apolipoprotein B, and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) are characteristics of dyslipidemia linked to obesity. By blocking 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase, statins with pharmacological characteristics increased their effectiveness in reducing LDL-C (Muscoli et al., 2022). Fibrates, which are derivatives of fibric acid, are thought to be one of the best treatments for atherogenic dyslipidemia since they raise HDL, decrease TG, and improve HDL levels.

As a member of the Caesalpiniaceae subfamily of the Fabaceae family, *Cassia fistula* is referred to locally as "Amaltas." Every portion of the plant has therapeutic qualities, such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, analgesic, and anti-arthritic. Anthraquinones, flavonoids, and derivatives of flavan-3-ol are among the several phenolic antioxidants found in *Cassia fistula*. The plant's bark demonstrated heightened antioxidant capacity. By preventing the generation of superoxide negative ions, the fruit pulp of this plant has anti-inflammatory properties (Bhakshu et al., 2023).

Materials and Methods

Plant collection and extraction

The leaves of *Cassia fistula* were gathered from the Faisalabad University of Agriculture. The leaves were collected, cleaned three times with distilled water, and then allowed to dry in the shade. Two weeks later, a grinder was used to ground the leaves into a coarse powder. Ten milligrams of the leaf powder were combined with one hundred milliliters of distilled water, and the mixture was heated to 75 degrees Celsius for half an hour while being constantly stirred. The solution was allowed to cool to room temperature before being filtered through muslin cloth and Whatman's filter paper No. 1. Following filtration, the filtrate was kept for later use at 4 C (Sajid et al., 2025b).

Qualitative phytochemical analysis

To determine the presence of different bioactive primary and secondary phytochemicals, the produced plant extract was put through a phytochemical analysis (Subhan et al., 2021).

Experimental Protocol

Thirty rats were randomly assigned to five groups for this investigation. During the 28-day experiment, G1, the normal control (NC), received the appropriate diet and water. For 28 days, G2 was maintained as the positive control and fed a regular diet. G3 had atorvastatin (PO) treatment and was in the standard group (SG). Treatment group one (CFE250) received a low dose (250 mg/kg) of *Cassia fistula* leaf extract (CFE) for 14 days, while treatment group two (CFE500) received a high dose (500 mg/kg).

Assessment of body weight

To assess the impact of treatments, the weight of each rat was recorded using a weighing balance on days 0, 7, 14, 21, and 28.

Lipid Profile

To estimate the lipid profile, the amounts of total cholesterol (TC), low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, triglycerides (TG), and high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol in serum were measured using commercially available calorimetric kits.

Health Markers

Using the proper calorimetric kits, the levels of kidney markers like creatinine and urea as well as the activity of liver markers like AST and ALT were measured in the serum.

Antioxidant level

Calorimetric kits were utilized to estimate antioxidant defense markers such as catalase (CAT) and superoxide dismutase (SOD).

Histopathology

The liver underwent histological examination. Hematoxylin and eosin stain (H&E) was used to

stain the samples after they had been fixed in a 10% formalin solution.

Statistical analysis

Using CRD, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to examine the data. Tukey's test was used for data multiple comparison at the 5% level of significance ($P \leq 0.05$).

Results

Phytochemical analysis

The qualitative phytochemicals analysis of *Cassia fistula* leaf extract showed the presence of different bioactive constituents given in table 1.

Table 1: Qualitative phytochemical analysis

Phytochemical	Result
Alkaloids	+
Flavonoids	+
Phenols	+
Tannins	+
Saponin	-
Carbohydrate	-
Glycoside	-

Body Weight

The experimental rats' body weight was recorded on weekly basis. Following a high-fat diet all groups showed a substantial rise in body weight ($p < 0.05$) except normal group in which progressive rise in

body weight was observed. Following 14 days of treatment, the low- and high-dose treated groups with *Cassia fistula* leaf extract showed a significant decrease in body weight.

Table 2: Body weight of experimental rats (Mean \pm S.D) in grams

Groups	Days				
	0	7	14	21	28
Normal Control	144.36 \pm 0.22	151.41 \pm 0.46	158 \pm 0.72	163.78 \pm 0.59	169.41 \pm 0.27
Positive control	151.26 \pm 1.17	159.39 \pm 1.47	170.41 \pm 1.11	182.49 \pm 0.89	191.38 \pm 1.02
Standard Group	157.71 \pm 1.71	167.24 \pm 1.63	178.14 \pm 0.88	181.71 \pm 0.98	184.72 \pm 1.12
CFE Low dose	166.19 \pm 1.17	173.37 \pm 1.51	181.36 \pm 2.04	183.17 \pm 0.96	187.12 \pm 1.45
CFE High dose	153.47 \pm 0.91	163.73 \pm 0.98	172.72 \pm 0.89	175.31 \pm 1.32	178.29 \pm 0.71

Determination of health markers

Statistical analysis revealed that the serum AST, ALT, creatinine and urea levels of positive control rats was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than those of normal control rats. However, following therapy with cholesterol-lowering drug

atorvastatin and *Cassia fistula* leaf extract, the serum AST, ALT, creatinine and urea levels were considerably ($p < 0.05$) decreased. A non-significant difference was observed between standard and high doses of *Cassia fistula* leaf extract.

Table 3: Health marker determination of experimental rats (Mean ± S.D)

Groups	Parameters			
	AST	ALT	Urea	Creatinine
Normal Control	115.72 ± 2.75	73.47 ± 2.34	14.27 ± 0.11	28.47 ± 1.79
Positive control	232.17 ± 1.79a	389.35 ± 3.09a	35.37 ± 0.47a	69.59 ± 0.69a
Standard Group	157.42 ± 2.47ab	121.21 ± 0.91ab	19.16 ± 0.27ab	39.21 ± 0.27ab
CFE Low dose	173.79 ± 2.19abc	163.17 ± 3.29abc	24.14 ± 0.89abc	48.58 ± 1.43abc
CFE High dose	159.32 ± 2.19ab	125.71 ± 1.19ab	18.74 ± 0.29ab	37.25 ± 0.72ab

Serum lipid profile

As seen in figure, statistical analysis shows that the total cholesterol, triglyceride and low-density lipoprotein levels of the positive control group rats were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher while high density lipoprotein level was significantly decreased than those of the normal control group.

A significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the serum level of TC, TG and LDL and a significant increase in HDL level in the groups treated with atorvastatin and those treated with *Cassia fistula* leaf extract was observed.

Figure 1: Determination of lipid profile. A; Total cholesterol, B; Triglycerides, C; LDL-level and D; HDL-level in serum. Level of significance ($p < 0.05$). A, B and C shows the significance of the difference of the Normal control, Positive control and Standard groups with other groups, respectively.

Antioxidant determination

Statistical analysis revealed a significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in SOD and catalase levels in the positive control group given high-fat diet throughout out experimental trial. When low (250 mg/kg) and high

(500 mg/kg) doses of *Cassia fistula* leaf extract were given to treatment groups, the level of SOD and catalase was significantly ($p < 0.05$) improved than that of the positive control group.

Figure 2: Determination of Antioxidants. A; Catalase level and B; SOD level in serum. Level of significance ($p < 0.05$). A, B and C shows the significance of the difference of the Normal control, Positive control and Standard groups with other groups, respectively.

Histopathology

Under a microscope, histopathological analysis of liver tissue reveals an excessive accumulation of fat cells in comparison to the normal control. Additionally, a high-fat diet causes the liver's major portal vein to expand, hepatocytes to change in morphology radially, and lymphocytes to infiltrate.

The histology results of the liver tissue, which are displayed below, validate the development of hyperlipidemia in the liver. In therapy groups, all of these alterations in the hyperlipidemic group are lessened. In comparison to the groups treated with plant extract, atorvastatin's effect on fat deposits is more successful.

Figure 3: Histopathology of liver tissue. A; Normal Control, B; Positive Control, C; Standard Group, D; Cassia fistula low dose (250mg/kg) and E; Cassia fistula high dose (500mg/kg).

Discussion

A metabolic disorder known as hyperlipidemia is indicated by increases in the plasma concentrations of various lipids and lipoprotein fractions, including serum total cholesterol (TC), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), triglycerides (TG), and a drop in high-density lipoprotein (HDL) levels. According to reports, the leading cause of death in developed countries and an important contributor to the progression of cardiovascular illnesses is hyperlipidemia (Alloubani et al., 2021). Hyperlipidemic people have greater levels of malondialdehyde, the byproduct of polyunsaturated fatty acid peroxidation. Lipid peroxidation and oxidative cell injury may arise from the overproduction of free radicals brought on by elevated MDA levels. Hyperlipidemia-related problems can potentially be connected to these outcomes. Hyperlipidemia is also associated with oxidative alteration of LDL and protein glycation, which raises lipid peroxidation products and causes oxidative stress. Antioxidant treatment may increase the body's capacity for antioxidants by slowing down the rate of peroxidation (Adwas et al., 2019).

Medicinal plants have been used extensively in many traditional medical systems throughout history (Aslam et al., 2024). The medicinal herb *Cassia*

fistula Linn., sometimes referred to as "Yellow Shower," is utilized in both traditional medicine and Ayurvedic medicine. As well as having pharmacological qualities like hepatoprotective, lipid lowering, anti-inflammatory in nature antipyretic, antimicrobial, antifungal, and antiparasitic effects, different plant parts contain different phytochemical constituents like saponin, glycosides, anthraquinone, saponin, steroids, and flavonoids. According to this review, *Cassia fistula* Linn. may help identify new bioactive natural compounds that will support the creation of medicinal goods (Jangid et al., 2025).

An incongruity between energy intake and expenditure leads to weight gain. Adiposity is caused by triglyceride accumulation in white adipose tissue as well as other tissues (Li and Spalding, 2022). In the current study, the positive control group showed a substantial increase in weight in comparison to the negative control group (Talumaa et al., 2022). A high-fat diet is often associated with the development of metabolic syndrome and dyslipidemia. A high-fat diet and the ensuing dyslipidemia are important contributors to oxidative stress, according to published evidence (Ismail et al., 2022). The results of the current study indicate low serum concentrations of HDL, an indication of

dyslipidemia, and elevated levels of TGs, vLDL, and serum cholesterol. Comparable outcomes for low blood HDL concentrations brought on by a high-fat diet and raised serum cholesterol, vLDL, and TG levels. Dyslipidemia plays a critical role in the development of atherosclerosis, a vascular disorder that causes heart attacks, strokes, and kidney damage, among other cardiovascular problems. Furthermore, cardiovascular illnesses are strongly associated with lipid disorders, especially elevated plasma cholesterol levels (Wazir et al., 2023).

In the arteries around the heart, LDL and vLDL stimulate the production of foam cells and lipid peroxidation (Gui et al., 2022). The primary causes of atherosclerosis and important markers of dyslipidemia include elevated TGs, TC, and vLDL. *Cassia fistula* leaf extract demonstrated a massive hypo-lipidemic effect, while the results of the current investigation demonstrated a significant drop in various treatment groups compared to the positive group. The importance of the phytochemicals—flavonoids, phenols, and saponins—found in the aqueous extracts of the *Cassia fistula* leaf may be the cause of this. The absorption of cholesterol is considerably hampered by these phytochemicals. Additionally, they interact with bile acids to produce insoluble complexes that increase fecal excretion and, ultimately, lower plasma cholesterol levels. These phytochemicals interact with bile acids to produce insoluble complexes that hinder the intestinal absorption of cholesterol. This led to a drop in the plasma concentration of plasma cholesterol because it enhanced the excretion of cholesterol in the feces (Collins et al., 2023).

Flavonoids, phenols, saponins, alkaloids, and other phytochemicals are abundant in *Cassia fistula* leaves. According to earlier research on different plant components, the high levels of phytochemicals found in them may be the cause of their role in lowering serum liver function enzymes. When CCL4 caused liver damage, sweet violet (*Viola odorata* L.) enhanced the activity of the liver enzymes ALT, AST, and ALP (Abbas et al., 2025; Batiha et al., 2023).

Oxidative stress and visceral fat accumulation are associated with metabolic syndrome. According to research, rats in diet models generated by obesity showed increased oxidative stress in the liver as a result of an excess of reactive oxygen species and

insufficient antioxidant capacity (Kazura et al., 2023). To quantify the level of oxidative stress in dyslipidemic rats relative to the normal group, we measure the levels of SOD and CAT in the rats' livers in this study. The results show that a high-fat diet causes increased oxidative stress in the rat's liver. The results of Zhang and colleagues' investigation into the oxidative stress caused by a high-fat diet in rats' livers were consistent with our findings (Zhang et al., 2022).

To examine the impact of plant extracts and a high-fat diet on the rat's liver, histopathology analysis of the liver was performed for each group. The central vein of the positive control group exhibits RBC infiltration and a compromised epithelial cell layer. The buildup of fat globules in the hepatocytes is another cause of liver steatosis. In the liver of rats fed a diet high in fat and sugar, Pahua-Ramos and colleagues also noticed micro and macrovesicular steatosis, which subsided when the rodents were fed avocado paste. Notably, in contrast to the positive group, our results unambiguously demonstrated restored hepatocytes and a decrease in hepatic steatosis. The phytochemicals that are found in the extracts may be the cause of this healing (Prajapati et al., 2024).

Conflict of interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Authors Contribution

M.K.S, A.I and A.G; Conceptualization and conduct research work. M.Y, S.N and S.Y; Data analysis and interpretation. E.A, R.I, M.S, M.R.S and M.A; Analysis, writing and review.

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